

Table S1. Sample information and bulk isotopic compositions and abundances of gases and dissolved inorganic carbon.

site name	Site abbreviation	Latitude (N)	Longitude (E)	Date (M/D/Y)	Water T (°C)	$\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{CH}_4^a}$ (‰)	$\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{CO}_2^a}$ (‰)	$\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}^a}$ (‰)	DIC (mM)	Gas composition (%) ^{b,c}			
										CH ₄	C ₂ H ₆	C ₃ H ₈	CO ₂
Chukou fault													
Yun-Shui Elementary School	YSES	23.3804	120.5285	11/16/17	23	-49.2	-21.3	-10.1	3.6	99.7	0.3	B.D.L	0.0
Chung-Lun Pond	CLP	23.3759	120.5583	11/14/17	26	-33.7	-2.5	1.8	235	13.2	0.1	B.D.L	86.7
Chung-Lun Spring	CLS	23.3770	120.5651	10/19/17	28	-34.9	-3.7	N.S	363	17.3	0.1	B.D.L	82.6
Chung-Lun Spring	CLS	23.3770	120.5651	11/14/17	26	-36.9	-2.3	5.4	271	18.6	0.1	B.D.L	81.2
Kuan-Tzu-Ling 02	KTL-02	23.3390	120.5023	11/14/17	29	-31.2	-4.6	-2.1	111	75.4	0.9	0.1	23.6
Kuan-Tzu-Ling 03	KTL-03	23.3383	120.5025	10/19/17	40	-36.4	-4.0	-1.6	109	83.9	0.7	B.D.L	15.4
Kuan-Tzu-Ling 03	KTL-02	23.3383	120.5025	11/14/17	27	-36.2	-5.4	2.2	79.4	79.8	0.8	B.D.L	19.4
Water and Fire	WF	23.3221	120.4828	11/14/17	26	-35.3	1.6	-15.8	5.1	97.0	2.4	0.4	0.3
Chishan fault													
Sin-Yang-Nyu-Hu 01	SYNH-01	22.8043	120.4100	11/13/17	31	-30.7	20.5	26.9	38.1	79.0	0.2	B.D.L	20.8
Sin-Yang-Nyu-Hu 02	SYNH-02	22.8030	120.4094	10/20/17	48	-34.6	-8.0	-1.7	34.1	96.9	1.7	0.4	1.1
Sin-Yang-Nyu-Hu 02	SYNH-02	22.8030	120.4094	11/13/17	41	-35.7	-8.9	-1.9	34.7	96.1	1.7	0.5	1.7
Sin-Yang-Nyu-Hu 02	SYNH-02	22.8030	120.4094	12/15/17	43	-48.5	-10.8	-2.8	N.S	95.3	1.9	0.5	2.3
Sin-Yang-Nyu-Hu 02	SYNH-02	22.8030	120.4094	11/22/18	42	-40.5	-15.2	N.S	N.S	95.9	1.6	0.4	2.0
Sin-Yang-Nyu-Hu 03	SYNH-03	22.8043	120.4100	11/22/18	34	-36.7	-15.9	N.S	N.S	98.3	0.4	0.1	1.3
Wu-Shan-Ding 01	WSD-01	22.7965	120.3977	12/15/17	26	-36.0	9.7	30.6	21.6	98.6	0.2	0.2	1.0

Wu-Shan-Ding 02	WSD-02	22.7965	120.4058	12/15/17	24	-35.7	8.9	18.5	N.S	99.3	0.1	B.D.L	0.6
Gutingkeng anticline													
Long-Chuan-Wo	LCW	22.9502	120.4270	11/13/17	38	-60.8	-3.9	7.0	9.3	97.8	0.1	B.D.L	2.1
Siao-Kun-Shui	SKS	22.8775	120.3857	10/20/17	26	-60.9	-2.2	4.3	40.9	99.1	0.1	B.D.L	0.9
Kun-Shui-Ping	KSP	22.7698	120.3356	10/20/17	26	-61.1	-0.1	7.7	48.2	97.3	0.2	B.D.L	2.5
Coastal Plain													
Wan-Dan	WD	22.3346	120.2717	07/08/19	63	N.S	N.S	N.S	9.3	87.8	0.7	0.1	11.4
Ta-Di-Shan	TDS	22.7695	120.2502	11/13/17	26	-60.8	-0.2	5.1	14.6	99.5	0.2	B.D.L	0.3
Ta-Di-Shan	TDS	22.7695	120.2502	12/15/17	25	-60.8	-3.9	7.2	11.5	98.8	0.1	0.1	1.0
Coastal Range													
An-Tung	AT	23.2813	121.3397	09/28/17	62	-41.1	-19.0	-21.0	0.4	97.2	1.3	0.1	1.3
An-Tung	AT	23.2813	121.3397	11/11/17	55	-47.8	-24.8	-29.5	0.4	98.6	0.5	0.9	0.0
Lo-Shan	LS	23.1872	121.2877	09/28/17	28	-46.5	-11.6	-5.9	0.5	99.8	0.1	B.D.L	0.0
Lo-Shan	LS	23.1872	121.2877	11/11/17	29	-35.2	-4.6	-11.0	0.6	98.0	0.3	B.D.L	1.7
Lei-Gong-Huo	LGH	22.9833	121.2073	08/04/16	25	-50.4	-0.3	N.S	0.4	99.8	0.2	B.D.L	0.0
Green Island 01	GI-01	22.6368	121.5024	09/29/17	45	-17.7	-16.2	-11.2	0.5	99.9	0.1	B.D.L	0.0
Green Island 03	GI-03	22.6371	121.5046	11/12/17	72	-16.7	-17.8	-12.5	B.D.L.	99.5	0.4	B.D.L	0.0
Four Way Closure and Formosa ridges													
GeoB23240-1, core 3P 107.6-108.9 mbsf	FWCR	22.0292	119.4807	11/15/18	N.S	N.S	N.S	N.S	N.S	99.8	0.0	0.0	0.1
Four Way Closure Ridge ^a													

GeoB23227-1, core 3P

21.5-22.7 mbsf

FR

22.0688

119.1713

11/07/18

N.S

N.S

N.S

N.S

N.S

99.7

0.0

0.0

0.1

Formosa Ridge^a

^aThe reported $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{CH}_4}$, $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{CO}_2}$, and $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ values were obtained using the IRMS hosted at National Taiwan University.

^bConcentrations of hydrocarbons and CO_2 for duplicate samples of FWCR and FR were also analyzed onboard *R/V SONNE* (Bohrmann et al. 2019).

^cGas compositions were normalized to the sum of methane, ethane, propane, and CO_2 .

^dB.D.L: below detection limit; N.S: no sub-sample.

Table S2. Methane isotopologue abundances, estimated formation temperatures, and accompanied bulk isotope compositions.

Site abbreviation	Sampling date (M/D/Y)	$\Delta^{13}\text{CH}_3\text{D}^a$ (‰)	T (°C) ^b	+/- (°C)	$\Delta^{12}\text{CH}_2\text{D}_2^a$ (‰)	T (°C) ^b	+/- (°C)	$\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{CH}_4^c}$ (‰)	$\pm 1\sigma$	$\delta^2\text{H}_{\text{CH}_4^c}$ (‰)	$\pm 1\sigma$
Chukou fault											
YSES	11/16/17	5.64	29	10/9	2.97	312	75/51	-52.25	0.01	-194.90	0.02
CLP	11/14/17	1.92	260	41/35	4.89	227	38/30	-33.90	0.01	-142.02	0.03
CLS	11/14/17	3.29	134	21/18	7.67	156	21/18	-36.55	0.01	-148.24	0.03
KTL-02	11/14/17	1.90	260	41/35	5.79	200	31/25	-34.02	0.01	-138.51	0.02
WF	11/14/17	6.01	17	9/9	7.71	156	21/18	-35.01	0.01	-142.53	0.02
Chishan fault											
SYNH-01	11/13/17	3.58	116	18/17	12.77	82	12/10	-37.28	0.01	-165.15	0.02
SYNH-02 ^d	10/20/17	2.13	236	37/31	5.47	208	33/26	-34.71	0.01	-141.83	0.04
SYNH-02 ^d	10/20/17	2.08	236	37/31	6.76	175	25/21	-35.03	0.01	-142.29	0.02
SYNH-02 ^d	10/20/17	2.17	225	35/29	7.15	168	24/20	-35.33	0.01	-143.56	0.03
SYNH-01	11/22/18	5.74	26	10/9	13.22	78	11/10	-36.91	0.01	-162.98	0.02
SYNH-02	11/22/18	3.29	134	21/18	5.67	203	31/26	-34.86	0.01	-142.77	0.02
SYNH-04	11/22/18	3.72	110	18/16	6.17	189	28/23	-34.93	0.01	-144.03	0.02
WSD-01	12/15/17	4.96	50	12/11	18.17	35	7/8	-36.09	0.01	-167.14	0.02
WSD-02	12/15/17	3.60	116	18/17	15.30	58	9/9	-36.01	0.01	-167.79	0.01

Gutingkeng anticline											
LCW	11/13/17	4.87	54	12/11	2.54	345	99/61	-52.73	0.01	-204.39	0.02
SKS	10/20/17	6.70	-2	7/8	4.04	261	51/37	-60.13	0.01	-206.37	0.02
KSP	10/20/17	3.23	141	22/19	0.49	686	513/242	-60.70	0.01	-199.05	0.02
Coastal Plain											
WD	07/08/19	2.53	196	29/26	6.32	187	27/23	-30.85	0.01	-142.77	0.03
TDS	11/13/17	2.86	163	24/22	1.17	490	460/121	-61.54	0.01	-200.55	0.02
Coastal Range											
AT	09/28/17	5.77	23	9/9	19.85	23	7/7	-40.19	0.01	-77.80	0.03
LS	09/28/17	3.27	99	17/15	13.77	76	11/10	-35.47	0.01	-122.06	0.02
LS	11/11/17	3.90	134	21/18	13.39	72	10/10	-35.36	0.01	-122.08	0.03
LGH	08/04/16	5.70	26	10/9	15.83	53	9/8	-50.51	0.01	-160.76	0.02
GI-03	11/12/17	3.62	116	18/17	14.53	65	10/9	-15.98	0.01	-78.35	0.03
Four Way Closure and Formosa ridges											
FWCR	11/15/18	6.89	-8	8/7	15.58	55	9/8	-69.06	0.01	-190.52	0.03
FR	11/07/18	7.08	-12	7/8	14.19	68	10/9	-69.08	0.01	-188.12	0.02

^aInternal precisions for $\Delta^{13}\text{CH}_3\text{D}$ and $\Delta^{12}\text{CH}_2\text{D}_2$ are less than $\pm 0.2\text{‰}$ and $\pm 0.6\text{‰}$ (1σ), respectively.

^bTemperature estimates based on $\Delta^{13}\text{CH}_3\text{D}$ and $\Delta^{12}\text{CH}_2\text{D}_2$ thermometers (Young et al., 2016, 2017).

^c $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{CH}_4}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}_{\text{CH}_4}$ values were measured using the Panorama hosted at the University of California at Los Angeles.

^dSYNH-02 10/20/17 are triplicate samples that were collected on the same date.

Table S3. Nitrogen bulk and clumped isotopic compositions of selected samples.

Site abbreviation	Sampling date (M/D/Y)	$\delta^{15}\text{N}$	$\pm 1\sigma$	Δ_{30}	$\pm 1\sigma$
KTL-02	11/14/17	-2.1	0.04	16.4	0.60
WSD-01	12/15/17	-1.2	0.03	11.1	0.43
AT	09/28/17	0.3	0.01	13.3	0.14
GI-01	09/29/17	3.5	0.01	1.8	0.18
GI-03	11/12/17	3.6	0.01	3.1	0.11

Table S4. Helium and neon abundances and helium isotopic compositions.

Site abbreviation	Sampling date (M/D/Y)	He isotope (Ra) ^a	He/Ne	He isotope (Ra) _c ^a	³ He/ ⁴ He	⁴ He conc. (ppm)	³ He conc. (ppm)
Chukou fault							
YSES	11/16/17	0.52	1.95	0.43	7.3E-7	13.9	1.0E-5
CLS	11/14/17	4.73	5.79	4.94	6.6E-6	32.9	2.2E-4
CLP	11/14/17	5.36	12.56	5.47	7.5E-6	12.3	9.2E-5
KTL-02	11/14/17	0.42	5.74	0.38	5.8E-7	24.4	1.4E-5
KTL-03	11/14/17	0.45	26.81	0.44	6.2E-7	33.5	2.1E-5
WF	11/14/17	0.17	17.11	0.15	2.3E-7	17.3	4.0E-6
Chishan fault							
SYNH-01	11/13/17	0.20	12.10	0.10	2.1E-7	17.9	3.7E-6
SYNH-02	10/12/17	0.18	16.46	0.16	2.5E-7	9.5	2.4E-6
WSD-01	12/15/17	0.12	0.39	-3.89	1.4E-6	5.3	7.2E-6
WSD-02	12/15/17	0.13	15.13	0.11	1.8 E -7	16.9	3.0E-6
Gutingkeng anticline							
LCW	11/13/17	0.8	0.40	0.20	1.1E-6	6.9	7.9E-6
SKS	10/20/17	0.10	36.46	0.09	1.4E-7	20.6	2.9E-6
KSP	10/20/17	0.39	47.79	0.39	6.4E-7	22.5	1.2E-5
Coastal Plain							

TDS	11/13/17	1.81	18.51	1.20	2.5E-6	22.4	5.6E-5
TDS	12/15/17	1.55	1.07	1.79	2.2E-6	12.5	2.7E-5
Coastal Range							
AT	09/28/17	2.4	4.20	2.5	3.3E-6	63.1	2.1E-4
LS	11/11/17	1.77	7.60	1.81	2.5E-6	7.9	2.0E-5
LGH	08/04/16	0.40	13.54	0.43	6.1E-7	9.8	6.0E-6
GI-01	09/29/17	6.76	8.77	6.98	9.4E-6	3720	3.5E-2
GI-03	11/12/17	6.67	29.99	6.73	9.3E-6	2100	2.0E-2

³Helium isotope compositions are expressed as the ³He/⁴He ratio in sample relative to that for the air (Ra). The analyzed ratios are further corrected with the removal of the air contribution assuming all the Ne derived from the air (Poreda and Craig, 1989) and expressed as (Ra)_c. The uncertainty is ±0.02 Ra (2σ).

Table S5. Isotopic compositions of water.

Site abbreviation	Sampling date (M/D/Y)	$\delta^2\text{H}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ (‰)	$\pm 1\sigma$	$\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ (‰)	$\pm 1\sigma$	$\epsilon_{\text{CH}_4\text{-H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{a}}$	T_{α}^{c} (°C)	$T_{\Delta 13\text{CH}_3\text{D}}^{\text{d}}$ (°C)	$T_{\Delta 12\text{CH}_2\text{D}_2}^{\text{e}}$ (°C)
Chukou fault									
YSES	11/16/17	-16.7	0.9	-1.1	0.3	-181.2		29	312
CLP	10/19/17	-25.4	1.0	4.5	0.1	-121.0	241	260	227
CLS	10/19/17	-26.2	0.5	4.5	0.1	-124.7		134	156
KTL-02	10/19/17	-18.7	0.6	4.8	0.1	N.S.			
KTL-02	11/14/17	-21.2	0.4	5.1	0.	-119.8	266	260	200
KTL-03	11/14/17	-31.5	0.7	-0.1	0.2	N.S.			
WF	10/19/17	-52.0	1.0	-8.1	0.1	N.S.			
WF	11/14/17	-52.5	0.4	-7.7	0.2	-95.0		17	156
Chishan fault									
SYNH-01	11/13/17	-23.4	0.6	6.1	0.1	-145.2	139	116	82
SYNH-01	12/15/17	-17.4	0.5	5.5	0.1	N.S.			
SYNH-02	10/20/17	-19.3	0.2	6.0	0.2	-125.4	241	236	208
SYNH-02	11/13/17	-22.7	0.6	6.4	0.	-124.4			
SYNH-02	12/15/17	-19.2	1.1	5.8	0.1	-125.7			
WSD-01	10/20/17	-16.0	0.9	5.1	0.2	N.S.			
WSD-01	12/15/17	-15.1	0.6	4.7	0.2	-154.4		50	35

WSD-02	12/15/17	-18.5	0.3	0.8	0.2	-152.1		116	58
Gutingkeng anticline									
LCW	11/13/17	-13.2	0.6	0.4	0.1	-193.8	54	54	345
SKS	10/20/17	-13.5	0.6	0.2	0.1	-195.5		-2	261
KSP	10/20/17	-10.8	0.9	1.1	0.1	-190.3		141	686
Coastal Plain									
WD	05/15/18	-22.1	0.3	6.0	0.1	-123.4		196	187
TDS	11/13/17	-14.9	0.5	0.8	0.1	-188.5		163	490
TDS	12/15/17	-11.3	0.8	0.5	0.2	N.S.			
Coastal Range									
AT	09/28/17	-30.7	0.8	-5.3	0.1	-48.6		23	23
AT	11/11/17	-35.6	0.9	-7.2	0.2	N.S.			
LS	11/11/17	-5.9	0.8	-0.6	0.1	-116.8		99	76
GI- 01	09/29/17	-1.0	1.0	-0.8	0.2	N.S.			
GI sea water	09/29/17	-4.1	0.6	-0.4	0.2	N.S.			
GI-02	11/22/17	-3.0	0.7	-0.5	0.1	N.S.			
GI-03	11/22/17	-3.1	0.8	-1.3	0.1	-75.5		116	65
Four Way Closure and Formosa ridges									
FWCR	11/07/18	N.S.		N.S.		N.S.		-8	55
FR	11/07/18	N.S.		N.S.		N.S.		-12	68

^a $\epsilon_{\text{CH}_4\text{-H}_2\text{O}}$ is defined as $(\alpha-1)\times 1000\%$.

^bN.S.: no sub-sample available.

^cTemperature estimates based on $\alpha(\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{CH}_4)$ thermometer (Horibe and Criag, 1995).

^dTemperature estimates based on $\Delta^{13}\text{CH}_3\text{D}$ thermometer (Young et al., 2016, 2017).

^eTemperature estimates based on $\Delta^{12}\text{CH}_2\text{D}_2$ thermometer (Young et al., 2016, 2017).

Table S6. Projected temperature/depth based on local geothermal gradient.

Site abbreviation	Sampling date (M/D/Y)	$\Delta^{13}\text{CH}_3\text{D}$	$\Delta^{12}\text{CH}_2\text{D}_2$	T- $\Delta^{13}\text{CH}_3\text{D}^{\text{a}}$ (°C)	T- $\Delta^{12}\text{CH}_2\text{D}_2^{\text{b}}$ (°C)	Projected depth (km)	Local geothermal gradient ^c (°C)
CLP	11/14/17	1.92	4.89	260	227	7-8	30
CLS	11/14/17	3.29	7.67	134	156	4-5	30
KTL-02	11/14/17	1.90	5.79	260	200	6-8	30
SYNH-02	10/20/17	2.13	5.47	236	208	8-9	25
WD	07/08/19	2.54	6.32	196	187	7-7	25
LS	09/28/17	3.27	13.77	99	76	2-3	30

^aTemperature estimates based on $\Delta^{13}\text{CH}_3\text{D}$ thermometers (Young et al., 2016, 2017).

^bTemperature estimates based on $\Delta^{12}\text{CH}_2\text{D}_2$ thermometers (Young et al., 2016, 2017).

^cLocal geothermal gradient values were adopted from Chi & Reed (2008).

^dThe project depth was calculated assuming a surface temperature of 20°C

Table S7. Temporal variability of methane isotopologue abundances and temperature estimates.

Site abbreviation	Sampling date (M/D/Y)	$\Delta^{13}\text{CH}_3\text{D}$ (‰)	T (°C)	+/- (°C)	$\Delta^{12}\text{CH}_2\text{D}_2$ (‰)	T (°C)	+/- (°C)	$\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{CH}_4}$ (‰)	$\pm 1\sigma$	$\delta^2\text{H}_{\text{CH}_4}$ (‰)	$\pm 1\sigma$	Source
SYNH-02-EW-1 ^a	02/15/17	3.22	163	24/22	8.25	146	20/17	-35.66	0.01	-149.90	0.02	Rumble et al., (2018)
SYNH-02-EW-3 ^a	02/15/17	2.90	141	22/19	9.24	120	16/14	-35.60	0.07	-149.97	0.04	Rumble et al., (2018)
SYNH-02 ^b	10/20/17	2.13	236	37/31	5.47	208	33/26	-34.71	0.01	-141.83	0.04	This study
SYNH-02 ^b	10/20/17	2.08	236	37/31	6.76	175	25/21	-35.03	0.01	-142.29	0.02	This study
SYNH-02 ^b	10/20/17	2.17	225	35/29	7.15	168	24/20	-35.33	0.01	-143.56	0.03	This study
SYNH-02	11/22/18	3.29	134	21/18	5.67	203	31/26	-34.86	0.004	-142.77	0.02	This study

^aSYNH-02-EW-1 and SYNH-02-EW-3 were collected from the same bubbling pool.

^bSYNH-02 10/20/17 are triplicate samples that were collected on the same date.

^cInternal precision for individual thermometers is the same as in Table S2.